

THE EFFECT OF INTERFACE ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS
OF MOLYBDENUM REINFORCED METAL COMPOSITES

Naohiro Igata and Akira Kohyama

Department of Materials Science, Faculty of Engineering,
University of Tokyo, 7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113,
Japan

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to clarify the role of interface layers on the mixture rules of Young's modulus, internal friction, tensile strength, ductility and strain rate sensitivity of strength using the three kinds of molybdenum reinforced metal composites.

Mo/Cu was prepared by infiltration method. In the case of Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni, hot press method was used.

The structure of interface in Mo/Cu varies at exact boundary layer, but Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni showed interdiffusion and diffusion layers. In Mo/Ti, within the interface layer α , β , ω and the mixture of the phases were observed and the width of the layer was $\sim 20\text{--}\sim 30\mu$. In Mo/Ni interface, there seemed to be several phases including intermetallic compounds within $\sim 10\mu$. Accordingly in Young's modulus, Mo/Ti deviated to smaller values and Mo/Ni deviated to higher values than the value obtained from the rule of mixture. As for tensile strength, the values deviated to stronger side from the simple rule of mixture in order of Mo/Cu, Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni. The work hardening coefficient and ductility until the load maximum were also analysed and the values n_c well coincided with the mixture rule. The higher ductility than the value of strain hardening coefficient in Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni was interpreted by multiple neckings. The conditions of initiation and growth of a new necking other than the original necking were briefly analysed using geometrical effect and the effect of strain rate sensitivities of strength. The importance of the interfacial bonding strength was understood through the strength and ductility of composites.

INTRODUCTION

It has become apparent that the interface between fiber and matrix plays a profound role in behavior of composite materials. Although a precise description of the interface is difficult, an understanding of the role of the interface in composite behavior and the ability to control the interface are considered to be important problems.

Concerning about these problems, many investigations have been performed, for example, from the stand points of mechanics or of microstructure⁽¹⁻⁷⁾. Yet, the studies on the role of the interface microstructure on mechanical properties of the fiber reinforced metal composites have been a few. (8,9)

The objective of this study is to clarify the role of interface on mixture rules of mechanical properties in molybdenum reinforced metal composites with regard to the microstructure of interface between fiber and matrix.

The systems of composites studied are chosen after Signorelli et al's¹ (8) classification, to be Mo/Cu, Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni for class 1 (not reactive not soluble), class 2 (not reactive, soluble) and class 3 (reactive), respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The three types of composites studied consisted of electrolytic copper (99.9%), electrolytic nickel(99.98%) and titanium(99.9%Ti-0.06%O) as matrices and molybdenum wire of 0.7mm diameter as fibers at volume fraction of 0 to 20%. Mo/Cu composite specimens were prepared with vertical type graphite mold by infiltration method in a vacuum of 1×10^{-5} torr. In the case of Mo/Ni and Mo/Ti, hot press method in a vacuum of 1×10^{-6} torr was used. The temperature for hot press was 880°C in Mo/Ti and 900°C in Mo/Ni for 1 hour. The composites studied were uniaxially reinforced with continuous fibers which were embedded in mono-layer structure. The specimen dimension was 1 mm(t) x 10 mm(w) x 100 mm(l). Co-axial tensile tests were performed in an Instron type testing machine at strain rates between 5×10^{-4} /sec and 5×10^{-2} /sec. To investigate deformation process, photo-etching gratings were used for tensile test specimens, of which the interval of the line was 50 μ . Internal friction and Young's modulus were measured through transverse vibration at 20°C. Electron probe micro analyser(EPMA) and Scanning electron microscope(SEM) were used for micro-analysis of interfaces and for fractography, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The structure of interface

In three kinds of composites, the distributions of fiber and matrix elements at interface were measured by EPMA corresponding to the microstructures as shown in Figs. 1,2 and 3. In Mo/Cu, from copper side to molybdenum side no extra phases nor interface layers were observed and at the interface, within the width of electron beam, the concentrations changed drastically from 100% to 0%, as shown in Fig.1. In Mo/Ti, from titanium side α phase, $\beta + \omega$ phases and ω phase were observed through both optical micro structure and EPMA analysis, as shown in Fig.2. In Mo/Ni, from nickel side α phase, $\alpha + \text{Ni}_4\text{Mo}$, $\text{Ni}_4\text{Mo} + \text{Ni}_3\text{Mo}$, Ni_3Mo , $\text{Ni}_3\text{Mo} + \text{NiMo}$, NiMo , $\text{NiMo} + \beta$ phase and β phase were estimated. In the case of Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni, Kirkendall effect is expected and it seems that vacancy clusters rich zone should be within molybdenum wire a little inner than the original interface. And the regions where the sum of the normalized X-ray intensity

Fig.1 EPMA results analysed across the interface of Mo/Cu.

Fig.2(a) Micro-structure of interface in Mo/Ti. (Right side is the molybdenum fiber)

Fig.2(b) EPMA result analysed across the interface of Mo/Ti. The shaded region indicates the vacancy cluster rich zone

Fig.3 EPMA results analysed across the interface of Mo/Ni. The shaded region indicates the vacancy cluster rich zone

Fig.4 SEM fractograph of Mo/Cu fractured surface after tensile test at room temperature

of two components becomes less than 100% are shown as shaded region in Figs. 2(b) and 3 which seem to be correspondent to the above mentioned vacancy cluster rich zones.

Microscopic features after fracture

In the microscopy of the longitudinal cross section after tensile deformation and fracture, multiple neckings of fibers were observed. In the case of Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni, the amount of each neckings and spacing of neckings were much smaller than in the case of Mo/Cu. In Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni, the radial resisting forces for necking were stronger due to interfacial layers and this would be the origin of the finer multiple neckings. Multiple necking phenomena were also observed by photo etching grating method both dynamically and after fracture.

The SEM photographs of fracture surfaces are shown in Figs. 4,5 and 6 for Mo/Cu, Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni respectively. In the three kinds of composites, the dimple fracture patterns were observed in both fiber and matrix. In Mo/Ti, the crevice and the longitudinal cracks in molybdenum fiber

Fig.5 SEM fractograph of Mo/Ti fractured surface after tensile test at room temperature

Fig.6 SEM fractograph of Mo/Ni fractured surface after tensile test at room temperature

existed and in the crevice the fibrous grain clusters were observed as shown in Fig.5. From the results of EPMA analysis, the location of crevice was identified to be along vacancy rich zones due to Kirkendall effect in molybdenum fiber. The longitudinal cracks in molybdenum fiber would be the evidence that the radial constriction force acted due to the strong interfacial bonding. In Mo/Ni, the similar features as in Mo/Ti was obtained.

Young's modulus and internal friction

As for Young's modulus, the comparison was tried by using normalized values $E_c - E_m / E_f - E_m$. For three kinds of composites the results are shown in Fig.7. In Mo/Cu, the experimental results were just as the mixture rule as shown in the next equation.

$$E_c - E_m / E_f - E_m = V_f \quad (1)$$

Fig.7 Normalized value of Young's modulus vs. fiber volume fraction. Solid lines indicate the calculated values after equation

Fig.8 Internal friction values at 20°C vs. fiber volume fraction. Solid lines indicate the mixture rule shown in Eq.(2) with $\zeta_i = 0$.

In Mo/Ti, the results deviated from the relation as shown in equation (1). This would come from the decrease of modulus of interface layer including ω phase which would be affected by stress.(10) The vacancy clusters due to Kirkendall effect would also act to decrease the modulus of composite. In Mo/Ni, the results deviated above the mixture rule. In this case, ΔE effect will be suppressed by the residual stress or resisting effect from the interface as the volume fraction of fiber increases. This increasing effect seems to be more dominant than the decreasing effect by Kirkendall effect.

As for internal friction, the observed values are plotted in Fig.8. These results are compared with the mixture rule as expressed in the following equation. (6)

$$\delta_{Tc} = \frac{\delta_{Tm} \cdot \{1 + \eta_i / \eta_m \cdot (1 - v_f)\} / \sqrt{1 + (v_f/1 - v_f)(M_f/M_m + S_f/S_m)}}{+ (v_f/1 - v_f)^2 (M_f/M_m) (S_f/S_m)} \quad (2)$$

In Mo/Cu, the results agreed with the calculated values from equation (2) assuming $\eta_i = 0$. In Mo/Ti, the results deviated above from the calculated values. This is showing that η_i (viscosity at interface) cannot be negligible. The origin of η_i would be the interface of β and ω phases which show stress induced transformation. This is also supported by that the increase of $\beta + \omega$ phases corresponds to the increase of internal friction.(11) In Mo/Ni, internal friction of composites deviated to lower side from the calculated values assuming $\eta_i = 0$ in equation (2). This would come from that ΔE effect decreases as the volume fraction of fiber increases.

Tensile strength

The tensile strength of three kinds of composites are shown as the function of fiber volume fraction in Fig.9. In this figure, a simple rule

Fig.9 Fiber volume fraction dependences of ultimate strength of composites. Solid lines indicate Mileiko's mixture rule.

of mixture and Mileiko's mixture rule (3) are shown as dotted line and solid line, respectively. In Mo/Cu and Mo/Ti, the tensile strength coincided with the calculated values by Mileiko's rule of mixture. In Mo/Ni, the observed values were higher than the calculated values by Mileiko's rule. Those tendencies would be due to fine structure of interface layers as shown in Fig.2(a) and bonding forces at interfaces. Further, the tendency seems to be closely related with fine multiple neckings in Mo/Ni.

Strain hardening coefficient and ductility

The strain hardening coefficient, n , is expressed as the next equation,

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \cdot \epsilon^n \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the mixture rule for strain hardening coefficient can be expressed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} n_c &= \frac{d \log \sigma_c}{d \log \epsilon} = \frac{d \sigma_c \cdot \epsilon}{d \epsilon \sigma_c} \\ &= \frac{n_f V_f \sigma_{of} \epsilon^{n_f} + n_m (1 - V_f) \sigma_{om} \epsilon^{n_m}}{\sigma_c} \\ &= n_f + F(V_f, \epsilon) (n_m - n_f) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$F(V_f, \epsilon) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{\sigma_f(\epsilon) V_f}{\sigma_m(\epsilon) (1 - V_f)} \right\}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

The equation (4) can be rewritten as the next equation.

$$n_c - n_f / n_m - n_f = F(V_f, \epsilon) \quad (6)$$

When we take ϵ as the strain at load maximum in composites and $\sigma_f(\epsilon)$ is taken from the extrapolation of strain hardening curve, n_c value can be calculated. From the relation of $n = \epsilon_u$ and Eq.(6), the ductility of composites at load maximum can be expressed as followings.

$$\epsilon_{uc} - \epsilon_{uf} / \epsilon_{um} - \epsilon_{uf} = F(V_f, \epsilon) \quad (7)$$

Fig.10 shows the normalized value in equations (6) and (7) as the function of fiber volume fraction. In this figure, the calculated values of n_c and ϵ_{uc} are shown as solid lines. In Mo/Cu, the values of n_c and ϵ_{uc} well coincided with the calculated values. In Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni, although the value n_c agreed with the calculated values, the value ϵ_{uc} was larger than n_c . In these cases multiple neckings were observed. And this high ductility in composites were interpreted by multiple neckings.

Strain rate sensitivity of strength

The strain rate sensitivity of strength was obtained by strain rate change method. It can be shown as the next equation.

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \cdot \dot{\epsilon}^m \quad (\text{at constant strain}) \quad (8)$$

Accordingly the value of m_c can be expressed as similarly as Eqs.(4) and (5).

Fig.10 Fiber volume fraction dependences of work hardening coefficient and ductility. Solid lines indicate rule of mixture.

$$m_c = \frac{d \log \sigma_c}{d \log \dot{\epsilon}}$$

$$= m_f + F(V_f, \dot{\epsilon})(m_m - m_f) \quad (9)$$

$$F(V_f, \dot{\epsilon}) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{V_f \cdot \sigma_{of} \dot{\epsilon}^{m_f}}{(1-V_f) \sigma_{om} \dot{\epsilon}^{m_m}} \right\}^{-1} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, Eq.(9) can be rewritten as

$$m_c - m_f / m_m - m_f = F(V_f, \dot{\epsilon}) \quad (11)$$

In the case of Mo/Ti, the experimental values were well coincided with the above mentioned mixture rule as shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11 Normalized values of strain rate sensitivity of strength vs. fiber volume fraction. Solid line indicates the rule of mixture for Mo/Ti.

Multiple neckings

Using Bridgeman's analysis, first we consider that apparent stress at necking can be expressed as the next equation.

$$\sigma_{app} = Y \cdot \{ [1 + (2R/a)] \cdot \ln \{ 1 + (a/2R) \} \} \quad (12)$$

This means that effective stress can be expressed in terms of σ_{app} as follows.

$$\sigma_z = (Y) = \sigma_{app} / \{ [1 + (2R/a)] \cdot \ln \{ 1 + (a/2R) \} \} \quad (13)$$

The stress at non necking region has the relation as

$$\sigma_o / \sigma_{app} = A_f / A_o \quad (14)$$

Therefore the ratio of stress at necking region and non-necking region can be expressed as follows

$$\sigma_z / \sigma_o = (A_o/A_f) / \{ [1 + (2R/a)] \cdot \ln \{ 1 + (a/2R) \} \} \quad (15)$$

It is possibly considered that when $\sigma_z / \sigma_o < 1$, a new necking will start beside the original necking, but when $\sigma_z / \sigma_o > 1$, only one necking will continue and multiple necking will not take place. Fig.12 shows σ_z / σ_o as the function of a/R assuming L is constant. This figure indicates that multiple necking can hardly happen with only geometrical effect but any effect from matrix.

In the case of composite materials, since the radial stress due to the constraint by surrounding matrix is negligible, $\Delta\sigma$ should be superposed to σ_z , then the next relation will be deduced.

$$\sigma_{zc} = Y (1 + \Delta\sigma / Y) \quad (16)$$

And for the formation of a new necking, σ_{oc} should be greater than Y . Therefore the condition that σ_{oc} becomes Y is correspondent to the condition of the next relation

Fig.12 Dependences of σ_z / σ_o as the function of A/R with constant L and A_o

$$\sigma_z / \sigma_0 < 1 + \Delta\sigma / Y \quad (17)$$

The value of $\Delta\sigma / Y$ becomes higher in the order of Mo/Cu, Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni. Therefore the multiple necking should take place easier in the same order. This tendency is also supported throughout this work.

From the standpoint of strain rate sensitivity of strength, the flow stress can be shown as the equation (8). This is translated to the next relation.

$$\sigma = \sigma'_0 \cdot \left(- \frac{dA}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{A} \right)^m \quad (18)$$

$$- \frac{dA}{dt} = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma'_0} \right)^{1/m} \cdot A \quad (19)$$

When we compare the necking speed of the original necking with that of a new necking, the followings will be deduced

$$\alpha = \frac{- \left(\frac{dA}{dt} \right)_{\text{new necking}}}{- \left(\frac{dA}{dt} \right)_{\text{original necking}}} = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma_z} \right)^{1/m} \cdot \frac{A_0}{A} \quad (20)$$

From this relation, the condition that new necking can develop α fold faster than original necking is deduced as follows.

$$\sigma_z / \sigma_0 < (1/\alpha)^m (A_0 / A_f)^m \quad (21)$$

In Fig.13, lines 1,2 and 3 show the critical conditions where the growth rate of a new necking becomes α fold higher than that of the original necking. This line is compared with the condition at which a new necking can take place. Assuming $\Delta\sigma$ is the half of the flow stress of matrix at the strain where fiber necks, $(1 + \Delta\sigma / Y)$ becomes 1.25 which is shown as line 4 in Fig.13. The region below the lines 1,2 or 3 and 4 indicates the region where a new necking possibly be initiated and grown.

Fig.13 Dependence of σ_z / σ_0 as the function of A/R with constant L and A_0 , which is shown as solid line. Lines 1 - 4 indicate the critical conditions for nucleations or growth of a new necking.

CONCLUSION

(a) Interfacial structures were investigated and in Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni, Kirkendall effect which came from unbalanced mutual diffusions between fiber and matrix was observed. The crevice was observed at the position of vacancy rich zone by Kirkendall effect. However this zone showed not so large effect on ductility of composite.

(b) As for Young's modulus and internal friction, the deviation from mixture rules were observed in Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni. In Mo/Ti the decrease of modulus and the increase of internal friction was interpreted by the structure of interface including ω and β phases. In Mo/Ni the deviations were related with the decrease of ΔE effect.

(c) As for tensile strength σ_u , in Mo/Ni the deviation from mixture rule by Mileiko was observed. This can be interpreted also by multiple neckings.

(d) As for strain hardening coefficient n_c and the strain at load maximum ϵ_{uc} , in Mo/Ti and Mo/Ni $\epsilon_{uc} > n_c$ relation was observed, and those phenomena seems to be interpreted only by multiple neckings. The higher ductility in Mo/Ni is related with the finer multiple neckings.

(e) As for strain rate sensitivity of strength, new rule of mixture was introduced and in the case of Mo/Ti this rule agreed with the experimental data obtained by strain rate change method.

(f) The conditions of initiation or growth of a new necking other than the original necking were analysed assuming simple conditions. The effects of interfacial bonding strength and matrix on multiple necking formation were briefly discussed.

NOMENCLATURE

E	: Young's modulus	Q^{-1}	: Internal friction
δ_T	: logarithmic decrement	M	: mass
η	: viscosity	S	: elastic force
V	: volume fraction	σ	: true stress
ϵ	: true strain	n	: work hardening coefficient
m	: strain rate sensitivity of strength	A_0	: fiber diameter at non-necking
A	: fiber diameter at necking	R	: radius of curvature at necking
Y	: deformation stress at necking	σ_{app}	: apparent stress at necking
σ_0	: co-axial stress at non-necking	σ_z	: co-axial stress at surface of necking
$\Delta\sigma$: radial force by matrix restraint at necking		
suffix c	: composite	suffix m	: matrix
suffix f	: fiber	suffix i	: interface
suffix u	: value at load maximum		

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